

Ultrasonic Investigation of Molecular Interaction in Binary Liquid Mixture of Polyethylene Glycol with Ethanol

Authors : S. Grace Sahaya Sheba, R. Omegala Priakumari

Abstract : Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is a condensation polymer of ethylene oxide and water. It is soluble in water and many organic solvents. PEG is used to make emulsifying agents, detergents, soaps, plasticizers, ointments etc. Ethanol (C₂H₅OH) also known as ethyl alcohol is a well known organic compound and has wide applications in chemical industry as it is used as a solvent for paint, varnish, in preserving biological specimens, used as a fuel mixed with petrol etc. Though their chemical and physical properties are well studied still because of their uses in day to day life the authors thought it is better to study some more of their physical properties like ultrasonic velocity hence adiabatic compressibility, free length, etc. A detailed study of such properties and some excess parameters like excess adiabatic compressibility, excess free volume and few more in the liquid mixtures of these two compounds with PEG as a solute and Ethanol as a solvent at various mole fractions may throw some light on deeper understanding of molecular interaction between the solute and the solvent supported by NMR, IR etc. Hence the present research work ultrasonics/allied studies on these two liquid mixtures. Ultrasonic velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) at room temperature and at different mole fraction from 0 to 0.055 of ethanol in PEG have been experimentally carried out by the authors. Acoustical parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), free volume (V_f), acoustic impedance (Z), internal pressure (π), intermolecular free length (L_f) and relaxation time (τ) were calculated from the experimental data. We have calculated excess parameters like excess adiabatic compressibility (β_E), excess internal pressure (π_E) free length(L_{fE}) and excess acoustic impedance(Z_E) etc for these two liquid mixtures chosen. The excess compressibility is positive and maximum around a mole fraction 0.007 and excess internal pressure is negative and maximum at the same mole fraction and longer free length. The results are analyzed it may be concluded that the molecular interactions between the solute solvent is not strong and it may be week. Appropriate graphs are drawn.

Keywords : Interaction, Induce dipole, mole fraction, Polarizability, Adiabatic Compressibility, Ultrasonic, Binary mixture.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014